

HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS. PART XXX. NEW SYNTHESIS OF 4-METHYLSCOPOLETIN AND 4-METHYLFRAXETIN

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Two new methods of the synthesis of 7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (4-methylscopoletin) have been described. The oxidation of 4-methyl-7-coumarinyl-methanesulphonate by alkaline potassium persulphate (Rib's method) furnished 4-methyl-6-hydroxy-7-coumarinyl-methanesulphonate which after methylation and subsequent demesylation afforded 4-methylscopoletin. The preferential monotosylation of 6:7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin gave the 7-*O*-tosyl derivative which on methylation and subsequent detosylation yielded 4-methylscopoletin. The oxidation of 4-methyl-7:8-coumarinyl-dimethanesulphonate by alkaline potassium persulphate yielded 4-methyl-6-hydroxy-7:8-coumarinyl-dimethanesulphonate which on methylation and subsequent demesylation furnished 4-methyl-6-methoxy-7:8-dihydroxycoumarin (4-methylfraxetin).

The synthesis of 7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin or 4-methylscopoletin (I) by the abnormal reaction of alkaline potassium persulphate on 6:7-dimethoxy-4-methylcoumarin was reported by (Miss) Bhavsar and Desai (*Ind. J. Phar.*, 1951, 13, 200), but Aghormurthy and Seshadri (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, 11B, 411) refuted our claim by stating their inability to confirm our results. We wish to emphasise that even now we are able to confirm our earlier observations which we publish in the experimental part for subsequent confirmation by others. (Miss) Bhavsar and Desai (*Curr. Sci.*, 1951, 20, 325; this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 141) published another synthesis of (I) by the oxidation of 4-methyl-7-coumarinyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate by alkaline potassium persulphate to 4-methyl-6-hydroxy-7-coumarinyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate (II), its methylation to 4-methyl-6-methoxy-7-coumarinyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate (III) and its subsequent detosylation. We have subsequently found that protection of the hydroxyl group by methanesulphonyl chloride (Mesylation) is preferable to *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (tosylation) as the oxidation product is obtained in an improved yield. The oxidation of 4-methyl-7-coumarinyl-methanesulphonate by alkaline potassium persulphate afforded 4-methyl-6-hydroxy-7-coumarinyl-methanesulphonate (IV) which on methylation and subsequent demesylation yielded (I). The preferential monotosylation of 4-methyl-6:7-dihydroxycoumarin furnished 4-methyl-6-hydroxy-7-coumarinyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate (II) which was methylated to 4-methyl-6-methoxy-7-coumarinyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate (III), and detosylated to (I).

For the synthesis of 4-methylfraxetin or 4-methyl-6-methoxy-7:8-dihydroxycoumarin (V), the mesylation of 4-methyl-7:8-dihydroxycoumarin by methanesulphonyl chloride afforded 4-methyl-7:8-coumarinyl-dimethanesulphonate which was oxidised by alkaline potassium persulphate to 4-methyl-6-hydroxy-7:8-coumarinyl-dimethanesulphonate (VI), which was methylated to 4-methyl-6-methoxy-7:8-coumarinyl-dimethanesulphonate (VII), the subsequent demesylation of which yielded 4-methylfraxetin (V), the synthesis of which from 4-methylumbelliferone by Aghormurthy and Seshadri (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3065) involved a number of stages. The protection

of the hydroxyl groups of polyhydroxycoumarins by the mesyl rather than the tosyl group during the nuclear oxidation of coumarins is advantageous as the steric factors suspected by (Miss) Bhavsar and Desai (*loc. cit.*) in the case of *O*-ditosyl derivatives of 4-methyl-7:8-dihydroxycoumarin and 4-methyl-5:7-dihydroxycoumarin, which did not undergo nuclear oxidation, are circumvented. We are exploring the extension of this method to the synthesis of other partially methylated ethers of polyhydroxycoumarins.

EXPERIMENTAL

Oxidation of 4-Methyl-6:7-dimethoxycoumarin and Formation of 4-Methyl-6-methoxy-7-hydroxycoumarin or 4-Methylscopoletin (I).—The solution of 4-methyl-6:7-dimethoxycoumarin (2 g.) in pyridine (40 c.c.) was cooled to 5°, and a mixture of the solution of KOH (4 g.) in water (40 c.c.) and potassium persulphate (4 g.) in water (100 c.c.) was slowly dropped with mechanical stirring during 2 hours; the stirring was continued for 6 hours when the mixture attained the room temperature. After 48 hours the deep brown alkaline solution was made acidic to Congo red by adding HCl (conc., 15 c.c.) when unchanged coumarin (0.2 g.) and an acidic substance, which melted indefinitely at 180°-207° (decomp.), separated out. The solution was thrice extracted with ether, when further quantities of the unchanged coumarin (0.2 g.) and acidic substance were obtained from the ethereal extract. The solution was then treated with sodium sulphite (4 g.), HCl (conc., 40 c.c.) and heated on a water-bath for half an hour. The cooled solution after removal of the suspended impurities was extracted thrice with ether, and the solid (0.7 g.) obtained from the ethereal extract was treated with 2% sodium bicarbonate solution to remove acidic impurities (0.2 g.) which melted at 210-15° and showed blue fluorescence in alkali solution. The substance, insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution (0.5 g.), was crystallised from ethyl acetate in colorless needles, m.p. 215-16°, undepressed on admixture with 4-methylscopoletin synthesised by Miss Bhavsar and Desai (*loc. cit.*). (Found: C, 63.8; H, 5.1. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₀O₄: C, 64.0; H, 4.9 per cent).

Its solution in water, alcohol, alkali and H_2SO_4 (conc.) showed strong blue fluorescence, but gave negative test with ferric chloride. It seems to be identical with Baker and Evans' 4-methylscopoletin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 374), m.p. 213° , developing green coloration with ferric chloride. Its methyl ether crystallised from dilute alcohol in white fibrous needles, m.p. $136-37^\circ$, undepressed by an authentic specimen of 6:7-dimethoxy-4-methylcoumarin.

4-Methyl-7-coumarinyl-methanesulphonate.—To a mechanically stirred solution of 4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (8.8 g.) and methanesulphonyl chloride (6 g.) in acetone (100 c.c.) a solution of sodium bicarbonate (9 g.) in water (50 c.c.) was added in four or five lots. After continued stirring for 4 hours, the mixture was poured in water when the sulphonate separated out as a solid. The solid was washed with 1% NaOH solution to remove the unchanged coumarin and was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 172° , yield 80%. It was soluble in usual organic solvents and dissolved in H_2SO_4 with a blue fluorescence. (Found: S, 12.8. $C_{11}H_{10}O_6S$ requires S, 12.6 per cent).

Oxidation to 4-Methyl-6-hydroxy-7-coumarinyl-methanesulphonate (IV).—To the cooled and mechanically stirred solution of the above sulphonate (3 g.) in pyridine (75 c.c.) solutions of KOH (6 g.) in water (60 c.c.) and potassium persulphate (6 g.) in water (150 c.c.) were gradually added alternately during 3 hours. The red solution with blue fluorescence was stirred for 6 hours and set aside for 24 hours. On making the solution acidic to Congo red by the addition of HCl (conc.), the unchanged material separated out. This was collected and the solution was extracted with ether which gave some more unchanged material (0.3 g.). The solution was then treated with sodium sulphite (6 g.) and HCl (conc., 80 c.c.), warmed on the water-bath for 1 hour and cooled. The solid separating was removed and ether extraction of the solution provided another lot. This solid was treated with 2% sodium bicarbonate solution and the residue (0.75 g.) crystallised from rectified spirit in white plates, m.p. 240° . (Found: S, 11.8. $C_{11}H_{10}O_6S$ requires S, 11.9 per cent). It dissolved in alkali with a deep yellow colour without any fluorescence. Its alcoholic solution showed blue fluorescence.

4-Methyl-6-methoxy-7-coumarinyl-methanesulphonate was prepared by refluxing the mixture of the above oxidation product (0.5 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g.), dimethyl sulphate (1 c.c.) and anhydrous acetone (50 c.c.) for 24 hours. The residue left after removal of the acetone was treated with water. The insoluble product was crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 170° . (Found: S, 11.2. $C_{12}H_{12}O_6S$ requires S, 11.3 per cent).

4-Methyl-6-methoxy-7-hydroxycoumarin or 4-methylscopoletin (I) was obtained by keeping the solution of the preceding compound (0.5 g.) in H_2SO_4 (conc., 15 c.c.) for 24 hours and pouring it over ice. The solid, purified through solution in dilute sodium hydroxide, crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles, m.p. 216° .

4-Methyl-6:7-dihydroxycoumarin was obtained by pouring the solution of (IV, 0.2 g.) in H_2SO_4 (conc., 6 c.c.) after 24 hours over ice. The crystallised product melted at 273° , undepressed by admixture with an authentic specimen.

4-Methyl-6-hydroxy-7-coumarinyl-p-toluenesulphonate (II).—A mixture of 4-methyl-6:7-dihydroxycoumarin (2 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (8 g.) and anhydrous acetone (75 c.c.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 7 hours. After removal of the acetone, the solid was treated with dilute NaOH solution when the ditosylated derivative (0.6 g.) remained insoluble. The alkali solution on acidification with HCl furnished a solid (1.2 g.) which crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 228°, undepressed by an authentic sample prepared by (Miss) Bhavsar and Desai (*loc. cit.*) by the oxidation of 4-methyl-7-coumarinyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate.

4-Methyl-6:7-coumarinyl-di-p-toluenesulphonate crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 160°. (Found: S, 12.6. $C_{21}H_{20}O_6S_2$ requires S, 12.8 per cent).

4-Methyl-6-methoxy-7-coumarinyl-p-toluenesulphonate (III) was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from dilute alcohol in white thin needles, m.p. 196°. (Found: S, 8.9. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{16}O_5S$:S, 8.8 per cent). Its melting point was undepressed by admixture with a sample prepared by (Miss) Bhavsar and Desai (*loc. cit.*). By pouring its solution in concentrated sulphuric acid (0.3 g. in 10 c.c. of the acid) after 24 hours over ice, it afforded 4-methylscopoletin, identified by m.p. and mixed m.p. with a specimen prepared by other methods.

Synthesis of 4-Methylfraxelin (V) from *4-Methyl-7:8-coumarinyl-dimethanesulphonate* was prepared in the usual manner from 4-methyl-7:8-dihydroxycoumarin (4 g.), methanesulphonyl chloride (5 g.), acetone (75 c.c.) and sodium bicarbonate solution (2.5 g. in 50 c.c. water). After usual purification it was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 222°, yield 3.5 g. (Found: S, 18.2. $C_{12}H_{12}O_6S_2$ requires S, 18.4 per cent).

Oxidation to 4-Methyl-6-hydroxy-7:8-coumarinyl-dimethanesulphonate (VI).—The solution of the preceding coumarin (3.5 g.) in pyridine (40 c.c.) was oxidised as usual, using a solution of KOH (8 g.) in water (80 c.c.) and potassium persulphate (8 g.) in water (200 c.c.), and the solution was worked up after 48 hours. After acidification to Congo red and extraction with ether, unchanged coumarin (2 g.) was obtained. The solution was treated with sodium sulphite (8 g.) and HCl (conc., 80 c.c.) and warmed on a water-bath for 30 minutes. The solution was extracted with ether six times and the dried ethereal extract afforded the oxidation product (0.5 g.), which after treatment with sodium bicarbonate solution crystallised from ethyl acetate in white needles, m.p. 228°. It dissolved in alkali with a deep yellow colour while its alcoholic solution gave blue fluorescence. (Found: S, 17.2. $C_{15}H_{12}O_6S_2$ requires S, 17.5 per cent). When its solution in H_2SO_4 (conc.) was poured over ice-cold water, 4-methyl-6:7:8-trihydroxycoumarin, m.p. 274°, was obtained. Its melting point was undepressed by admixture with a specimen prepared by (Miss) Bhavsar and Desai (*loc. cit.*); Parikh and Sethna (*this Journal*, 1950, 27, 369), and Sawhney, Seshadri and Thiruvengadam (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1951, 33A, 11) also record the same m.p.

4-Methyl-6-methoxy-7:8-coumarinyl-dimethanesulphonate (VII) was obtained by methylating (VI, 0.4 g.) with dimethyl sulphate (1 c.c.) in acetone (50 c.c.) in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g.) as usual. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in white plates, m.p. 218°. (Found: S, 16.8. $C_{18}H_{14}O_6S_2$ requires S, 16.9 per cent).

4-Methylfraxetin or *4-methyl-6-methoxy-7:8-dihydroxycoumarin* (V).—A solution of the preceding coumarin (VII, 0.2 g.) in H_2SO_4 (conc., 6 c.c.) was poured over ice-cold water after 24 hours. The solid crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 259-60°. It dissolved in dilute alkali with a yellow colour and its alcoholic solution developed a blue-green colour with ferric chloride. The m.p. as well as the colour reactions agree with those reported by Aghormurthy and Seshadri (*loc. cit.*).

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